

HBeAg Negativity is Associated with a Higher Risk of Liver-Related Death in Patients with Chronic Hepatitis B Related Liver Cirrhosis

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Background and aims: Few studies reported the association between the survival of patients with chronic hepatitis B (CHB)-related liver cirrhosis (LC) and hepatitis B e antigen (HBeAg) state.

Methods: Three hundred and ninety-eight CHB-LC patients from two institutions were included. To adjust for selection bias, propensity score matching (PSM) with 1:1 ratio was used to balance clinical features between HBeAg-positive and HBeAg-negative CHB-LC patients. The related factors of liver-related death were identified by cox regression analysis, while the difference of survival was analyzed using Kaplan–Meier curves.

Results: Two hundred and eighty-eight (72.4%) CHB-LC patients were HBeAg negative, and the median follow-up time was 33.9 months. Fifty-two liver-related deaths occurred during the follow-up period. The liver-related mortality in HBeAg-negative CHB-LC patients was comparable with HBeAg-positive patients before PSM (14.2% vs. 22.3%, $P = 0.094$). After PSM for age, sex, platelet count, ALT level, and HBV DNA, 77 patients were matched in each group. Higher liver-related mortality was observed in patients with HBeAg-negative CHB-LC than those of HBeAg-positive CHB-LC patients (39.6% vs. 18.7%, $P = 0.019$). Patients with decompensated LC had similar results. Furthermore, HBeAg-negative state was identified as a significantly risk factor of liver-related mortality (HR, 3.032; 95% CI, 1.232–7.460; $P = 0.016$).

Conclusions: HBeAg-negative state may be an independent risk factor of liver-related mortality in patients with CHB-LC.

Keywords: HBeAg; Hepatitis B; Cirrhosis; Propensity score matching.

Introduction

Approximately 290 million patients are suffering from chronic hepatitis B virus (HBV) worldwide, which is one of the most common causes of liver cirrhosis (LC)^[1–3]. About 2%–10% of patients with chronic hepatitis B (CHB) may progress to cirrhosis each year^[4,5]. The annual incidence of hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) is 3%–6% in LC patients, while the 5-year cumulative survival rate is only 14%–35% in patients with decompensated LC^[4–6]. Previous studies have demonstrated that age, serum HBV DNA load, and antiviral therapy affect the clinical outcomes of

CHB-related LC^[7,8].

Serum hepatitis B e antigen (HBeAg) has always been regarded as a significant biomarker reflecting the disease immune state of CHB^[2,3]. HBeAg positivity indicates active viral replication, which may promote the incidence of LC and HCC^[9–11]. Patients with HBeAg-positive CHB usually present high load of HBV DNA, which has been demonstrated to be associated with high risk of liver-related advanced events^[9,10]. HBeAg seroconversion or loss represents a partial immune control of CHB infection, but HBV mutations are common in HBeAg-negative patients^[3,12,13]. Numerous reports have shown that HBeAg-negative CHB patients have more advanced liver disease and a higher risk of LC and HCC compared to HBeAg-positive CHB patients^[14–17]. Our previous study also showed that liver fibrosis degree was more severe in patients with HBeAg negativity than those of HBeAg-positive patients^[17]. However, the association of HBeAg status with the prognosis of CHB-LC patients remains unclear.

Although HBeAg state was reported to be correlated with prognosis of CHB, the association of HBeAg state and liver-related outcome in patients with CHB-LC is inconsistent^[9,17]. Confounding factors including age, gender, and HBV DNA levels may be

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responsible for the inconsistent results. Therefore, we compared liver-related mortality in HBeAg-positive CHB-LC patients with HBeAg-negative CHB-LC patients by the propensity score matching (PSM).

Methods

Patients

We retrospectively included patients with CHB-LC from two institutions in Jiangsu province, China, between January 2011 and March 2017. The cirrhosis was diagnosed by abdominal ultrasound, computed tomography, or magnetic resonance imaging. The definition of decompensated LC was the presence of ascites (AS), hepatic encephalopathy (HE) or esophageal variceal bleeding (EVB)^[18]. Patients with concurrent the following conditions were excluded: (1) other chronic liver diseases, including viral hepatitis, autoimmune liver disease, alcoholic liver disease, and nonalcoholic fatty liver disease; (3) HCC or other malignant tumor at or before the enrollment; (4) other systemic serious illness. The study followed the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the ethics committee of local hospitals.

Data collection and follow-up

The clinical features were collected from electronic medical records. HBeAg status was tested by using commercial kits, and HBV DNA was detected using the TaqMan polymerase chain reaction assay.

The primary study endpoint was liver-related mortality. The causes of liver-related death in this study included EVB, HE, spontaneous peritonitis, liver failure, and HCC. Survival time of patients was defined from the enrollment to the end of follow-up.

The interval was censored at the time of the last follow-up for surviving patients or at the time of death for deceased patients. The clinical outcome of each patient was obtained by a review of institutional records, patient interviews, or interviews with family members.

Statistical analysis

Continuous variables were expressed as a median (interquartile range [IQR]) and compared using the Mann–Whitney *U* test (for non-normal distribution) or *t* test (for normal distribution). Categorical variables were presented as frequencies or percentages, and were compared using the chi-square test or Fisher's exact test. The risk factors of liver-related mortality were identified by univariate and multivariate Cox proportional hazards model. Survival estimates were carried out using the Kaplan–Meier method, and were compared using the log-rank test. To balance potential bias between HBeAg-positive and HBeAg-negative patients, the PSM method at a 1:1 ratio was used in our study. A *P* value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. The data analysis was performed by SPSS version 22.0 software (IBM, Armonk, NY).

Results

Study population

Six hundred and twenty-three patients with CHB-LC were included. According to the exclusion criteria, eighty-two patients were excluded. Eight-seven patients with lost to follow-up and 56 patients with insufficiency of data were also excluded. The patient selection process is shown in Fig. 1. Overall, 398 patients with CHB-LC were included for the final analysis.

The clinical features of study subjects are presented in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Flow diagram of patient selection.

Two hundred and eighty-eight (72.4%) patients were HBeAg negative. HBeAg-negative patients were older than HBeAg-positive patients. The age (median 52.0 vs. 45.0 years; $P = 0.003$) and HBV DNA levels ($3.6 \text{ Log}_{10} \text{ IU/mL}$ vs. $2.7 \text{ Log}_{10} \text{ IU/mL}$, $P = 0.020$) in HBeAg-positive patients were higher than those of HBeAg-negative patients, while more patients had EVB in HBeAg-negative patients (25% vs. 13.6%, $P = 0.014$). However, there was no significant difference in other clinical characteristics between HBeAg-positive and HBeAg-negative patients, including gender, platelet counts, alanine aminotransferase (ALT) level, prothrombin time (PT), Child–Turcotte–Pugh (CTP) score, model for end-stage liver disease (MELD) score, and the proportion of patients with antiviral therapy. PSM was performed to adjust for the potential confounding factors between HBeAg-positive and HBeAg-negative patients. Age, gender, platelet count, ALT level, and HBV DNA were imputed, which yielded 77 matched pairs in the present study. The clinical characteristics were comparable between these two groups after PSM (Table 2).

Independent risk factors of liver-related mortality before PSM

In the univariate Cox analysis, age (hazard ratio [HR]: 1.064; 95% confidence interval [CI]: 1.039–1.089; $P < 0.001$), total bilirubin level (Tbil) (HR: 1.007; 95% CI: 1.004–1.010; $P < 0.001$), albumin (ALB) level (HR: 0.883; 95% CI: 0.846–0.922; $P <$

0.001), CTP score (HR: 1.451; 95% CI: 1.300–1.618; $P < 0.001$), and MELD score (HR: 1.126; 95% CI: 1.071–1.184; $P < 0.001$) were associated with liver-related mortality. These variables were input into the multivariate Cox analysis. The results indicated that age (HR: 1.055; 95% CI: 1.030–1.079; $P < 0.001$) and CTP score (HR: 1.340; 95% CI: 1.082–1.658; $P = 0.007$) were positively associated with liver-related mortality among CHB-LC patients (Table 3).

Independent risk factors of liver-related mortality after PSM

After PSM, the univariate analysis results revealed that age, antiviral therapy, Tbil level, ALB level, HBeAg negative status, CTP score, and MELD score were associated with liver-related mortality. Further multivariate Cox analysis revealed that age (HR: 1.083; 95% CI: 1.045–1.123; $P < 0.001$), HBeAg negative status (HR: 3.032; 95% CI: 1.232–7.460; $P = 0.016$), and CTP score (HR: 1.559; 95% CI: 1.157–2.100; $P = 0.004$) were independent risk factors of liver-related mortality, while antiviral therapy (HR: 0.279; 95% CI: 0.112–0.695; $P = 0.006$) was a protective factor against liver-related mortality (Table 4).

Cumulative mortality in patients with CHB-LC according to the HBeAg status

The median follow-up time of the study population was 33.9 (IQR 21.6–48.8) months. A total of 52 liver-related deaths were

Table 1. Baseline characteristics of patients with chronic hepatitis B-related liver cirrhosis before propensity score matching.

Characteristics	HBeAg (-) patients (n=288)	HBeAg (+) patients (n=110)	P value
Age (yr)	52.0 (45.8, 59.3)	45.0 (40.0, 55.0)	0.003
Male (%)	215 (74.7)	78 (70.9)	0.448
WBC ($\times 10^9/\text{L}$)	3.8 (2.7, 5.5)	3.5 (2.5, 5.7)	0.471
Hb (g/L)	119.0 (95.8, 140.0)	123.0 (102.0, 142.0)	0.133
PLT ($\times 10^9/\text{L}$)	74.5 (44.0, 119.5)	64.0 (46.0, 105.0)	0.243
Tbil ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	23.0 (15.3, 38.9)	27.4 (19.5, 44.3)	0.084
ALT (U/L)	34.5 (22.6, 60.0)	41.0 (28.0, 61.0)	0.063
AST (U/L)	43.2 (28.1, 68.1)	49.0 (32.0, 71.7)	0.151
ALB (g/L)	33.0 (29.3, 39.4)	35.0 (30.2, 40.6)	0.237
Cr ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	62.4 (55.0, 71.8)	58.0 (49.6, 68.6)	0.075
PT (s)	15.4 (14.1, 17.2)	15.6 (14.6, 17.3)	0.318
HBV DNA ($\text{Log}_{10} \text{ IU/mL}$)	2.7 (2.7, 4.7)	3.6 (2.7, 5.7)	0.020
CTP score	7.0 (5.0, 8.0)	7.0 (5.0, 8.0)	0.881
MELD score	7.3 (4.2, 10.6)	7.9 (4.3, 10.8)	0.621
HE (%)	17 (5.9)	4 (3.6)	0.366
Ascites (%)	114 (39.6)	48 (43.6)	0.462
EVB (%)	72 (25.0)	15 (13.6)	0.014
Antiviral therapy (%)	195 (67.7)	83 (75.5)	0.132
DCC (%)	201 (69.8)	77 (70.0)	0.968

WBC: white blood cell, Hb: hemoglobin, PLT: platelet; Tbil, total bilirubin, ALT: alanine aminotransferase, AST: aspartate aminotransferase, ALB: albumin, Cr: creatinine, PT: prothrombin time, CTP: Child–Turcotte–Pugh, MELD: model for endstage liver disease, HE: hepatic encephalopathy, EVB: esophageal variceal bleeding, DCC: decompensated cirrhosis, HBeAg, hepatitis B e antigen.

Table 2. Clinical features of patients with chronic hepatitis B-related liver cirrhosis after propensity score matching.

Characteristics	HBeAg (-) patients (n=77)	HBeAg (+) patients (n=77)	P value
Age (yr)	50.0 (43.0, 57.0)	47.0 (41.0, 56.0)	0.582
Male (%)	56 (72.7)	57 (74.0)	0.855
WBC ($\times 10^9/L$)	3.6 (2.7, 5.3)	3.3 (2.5, 5.8)	0.840
Hb (g/L)	122.0 (105.0, 145.5)	123.0 (101.5, 142.5)	0.865
PLT ($\times 10^9/L$)	83.0 (46.5, 118.0)	64.0 (46.0, 102.5)	0.143
Tbil ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	23.1 (16.2, 44.0)	27.5 (19.3, 45.4)	0.307
ALT (U/L)	34.5 (22.6, 60.0)	41.0 (28.0, 61.0)	0.437
AST (U/L)	43.2 (28.1, 68.1)	49.0 (32.0, 71.7)	0.201
ALB (g/L)	34.3 (30.3, 41.8)	34.1 (30.0, 40.5)	0.496
Cr ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	62.1 (56.0, 71.6)	57.5 (49.7, 69.3)	0.078
PT (s)	15.7 (14.4, 17.9)	15.6 (14.6, 17.7)	0.868
HBV DNA (Log_{10} IU/mL)	3.3 (2.7, 5.1)	3.3 (2.7, 5.3)	0.921
CTP score	7.0 (5.0, 8.0)	7.0 (5.0, 8.5)	0.865
MELD score	7.8 (4.0, 11.1)	7.9 (4.4, 10.9)	0.935
HE (%)	5 (6.5)	3 (3.9)	0.468
Ascites (%)	37 (48.1)	33 (42.9)	0.517
EVB (%)	5 (6.5)	8 (10.4)	0.385
Antiviral therapy (%)	67.0 (87.0)	63.0 (81.8)	0.374
DCC (%)	50 (64.9)	50 (64.9)	1

WBC: white blood cell, Hb: hemoglobin, PLT: platelet, Tbil: total bilirubin, ALT: alanine aminotransferase, AST: aspartate aminotransferase, ALB: albumin, Cr: creatinine, PT: prothrombin time, CTP: Child-Turcotte-Pugh, MELD: model for endstage liver disease, HE: hepatic encephalopathy, EVB: esophageal variceal bleeding, DCC: decompensated cirrhosis, HBeAg: hepatitis B e antigen.

Table 3. Cox regression analysis for survival of patients with chronic hepatitis B-related liver cirrhosis before propensity score matching.

Variables	Univariate		Multivariate	
	HR (95% CI)	P	HR (95% CI)	P
Age (yr)	1.064 (1.039, 1.089)	<0.001	1.053 (1.028, 1.078)	<0.001
Sex				
female	reference			
male	1.087 (0.580, 2.036)	0.795		
Antiviral therapy				
no	reference			
yes	0.741 (0.421, 1.304)	0.299		
PLT ($\times 10^9/L$)	0.999 (0.994, 1.003)	0.482		
Tbil ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	1.007 (1.004, 1.010)	<0.001	1.002 (0.995, 1.008)	0.607
ALB (g/L)	0.883 (0.846, 0.922)	<0.001	0.960 (0.901, 1.023)	0.213
ALT (U/L)	0.999 (0.995, 1.002)	0.414		
AST (U/L)	1.000 (0.998, 1.003)	0.868		
Cr ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	1.005 (0.991, 1.019)	0.469		
HBV DNA (Log_{10} IU/mL)	0.933 (0.751, 1.160)	0.534		
HBeAg status				
positive	reference			
negative	1.876 (0.915, 3.849)	0.086	1.308 (0.626, 2.736)	0.475
CTP score	1.451 (1.300, 1.618)	<0.001	1.346 (1.086, 1.668)	0.007
MELD score	1.126 (1.071, 1.184)	<0.001	0.990 (0.910, 1.078)	0.822

PLT: platelet, Tbil: total bilirubin, ALT: alanine aminotransferase, AST: aspartate aminotransferase, ALB: albumin, Cr: creatinine, CTP: Child-Turcotte-Pugh, MELD: model for end-stage liver disease, AT: antiviral therapy, HBeAg: hepatitis B e antigen, HR: hazard ratio, CI: confidence interval.

Table 4. Cox regression analysis for liver-related mortality of patients with chronic hepatitis B-related liver cirrhosis after propensity score matching.

Variables	Univariate		Multivariate	
	HR (95% CI)	P value	HR (95% CI)	P value
Age (yr)	1.076 (1.043, 1.110)	<0.001	1.083 (1.045, 1.123)	<0.001
Sex				
female	reference			
male	1.292 (0.521, 3.204)	0.580		
Antiviral therapy				
no	reference			
yes	0.351 (0.153, 0.802)	0.013	0.279 (0.112, 0.695)	0.006
PLT ($\times 10^9/L$)	1.000 (0.994, 1.006)	0.942		
Tbil ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	1.006 (1.002, 1.010)	0.001	1.001 (0.993, 1.010)	0.744
ALB (g/L)	0.906 (0.852, 0.963)	0.002	1.070 (0.972, 1.177)	0.166
ALT (U/L)	0.998 (0.994, 1.003)	0.450		
AST (U/L)	0.999 (0.995, 1.003)	0.635		
Cr ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	1.005 (0.985, 1.026)	0.624		
HBV DNA (Log_{10} IU/mL)	0.884 (0.677, 1.154)	0.363		
HBeAg status				
positive	reference			
negative	2.859 (1.207, 6.770)	0.017	3.032 (1.232, 7.460)	0.016
CTP score	1.459 (1.249, 1.704)	<0.001	1.559 (1.157, 2.100)	0.004
MELD score	1.165 (1.077, 1.261)	<0.001	1.020 (0.895, 1.163)	0.766

PLT: platelet, Tbil: total bilirubin, ALT: alanine aminotransferase, AST: aspartate aminotransferase, ALB: albumin, Cr: creatinine, CTP: Child-Turcotte-Pugh, MELD: model for end-stage liver disease, AT: antiviral therapy, HBeAg: hepatitis B e antigen, HR: hazard ratio, CI: confidence interval.

recorded at the end of follow-up. Before PSM, the cumulative mortality rate of HBeAg-negative patients was 22.3%, which was slightly higher than that of HBeAg-positive patients (14.2%) ($P = 0.094$). However, after PSM, the cumulative mortality rate in HBeAg-negative patients was higher than HBeAg-positive patients (39.6% vs. 18.7%, $P = 0.019$) during a median follow-up period of 32.1 months (Fig. 2).

Further survival analysis was performed in patients with decompensated LC (Fig. 3). The cumulative mortality rate in both HBeAg-positive and HBeAg-negative groups was comparable before PSM, while HBeAg-negative patients had a higher cumulative mortality rate than HBeAg-positive patients after PSM (51.0% vs. 27.2%, $P = 0.022$). Given that very few deceased patients were observed among those with compensated LC, the subgroup analysis regarding cumulative mortality rate between these two groups was not conducted.

Discussion

In the present study, we analyzed the impact of HBeAg status on liver-related mortality in CHB-LC patients. The results showed that liver-related mortality in was comparable between patients with HBeAg-negative and HBeAg-positive, and HBeAg state was not associated with long-term survival of patients with CHB-LC in the entire study group. However, after adjusting for the po-

tential confounders between these two groups by PSM method, HBeAg negativity was an independent risk factor of liver-related mortality, and patients with HBeAg negativity had a worse prognosis than those of patients with HBeAg positivity. Overall, our study demonstrated that liver-related mortality in patients with HBeAg-negative CHB-LC was higher than those of patients with HBeAg-positive CHB-LC.

HBeAg state is closely correlated with host immune status of CHB. This biomarker suggests active HBV replication with persistent liver inflammation and liver damage^[19]. HBeAg state is also correlated to long-term prognosis of CHB patients. A previous study reported that the presence of HBeAg was associated with an increased risk of HCC^[10]. A large study has reported that patients with CHB had a favorable prognosis after HBeAg seroconversion compared with persistent HBeAg-positive patients^[20]. Sun et al. reported that HBeAg positive CHB-related HCC patients had a higher risk of early recurrence and worse prognosis after curative resection^[21]. However, the proportion of patients with LC was higher and the degree of liver damage was more severe in HBeAg-positive patients than in HBeAg-negative patients^[21]. Another large study, which enrolled 11,893 male CHB patients, found that HBeAg positivity was positively associated with the incidence of HCC during 92,359 person-years of follow-up^[10]; however, this study did not consider the impact of gender. However, inconsistent results were reported in previous studies. Choi et al. reported that the presence of HBeAg state was not as-

Fig. 2. Comparisons of Kaplan–Meier curve of survival from liver-related mortality between HBeAg-positive and HBeAg-negative CHB-LC patients.

A. Before propensity score matching.
 B. After propensity score matching.

Fig. 3. Comparisons of Kaplan–Meier curve of survival from liver-related mortality between HBeAg-positive and HBeAg-negative decompensated cirrhosis patients.

A. Before propensity score matching.
 B. After propensity score matching.

sociated with prognosis of patients with CHB-related HCC after curative resection^[22]. Our previous study demonstrated that HBeAg-negative state was associated with more severe liver fibrosis in patients with CHB^[17]. In the present study, to control for the potential influencing factors, we used PSM method to evaluate the impact of HBeAg status on long-term prognosis in CHB-LC patients. The clinical features in both groups were comparable after PSM, including age, gender, platelet count, ALT level, and HBV DNA level. Our results revealed that HBeAg-negative patients had a lower survival rates than those of patients with HBeAg-positive during a median follow-up of 33.9 months, and HBeAg negative state was identified as a risk factor of liver-related mortality. We also demonstrated that antiviral treatment might be significantly associated with lower liver-related mortality in CHB-LC patients, which is consistent with previous studies^[7,8].

The potential mechanism remains unclear. Previous studies reported that mutations in precore or basic core promoter regions were more common in HBeAg-negative patients, and these were

documented to be associated with adverse outcomes in CHB patients^[23–26]. HBV genome mutation increases the host immune response to virus-infected hepatocytes by promoting hepatocyte apoptosis and regeneration, thereby resulting in continuous or recurrent liver damage. A retrospective study revealed that 24% of the CHB patients achieved HBeAg seroconversion experienced HBeAg-negative hepatitis after a median follow-up period of 8.6 years and 87% of these patients had a precore mutation^[20]. In addition, HBV core promoter mutations cumulatively enhance the replication of viral genome, leading to a higher viral load in hepatocytes compared with wild-type HBV, thereby aggravating liver damage and resulting in liver fibrosis, LC, and HCC^[27]. However, the exact mechanisms need to be confirmed in the future studies.

Although previous studies have reported the relationship of HBeAg status with prognosis in CHB patients^[9,10], we provided additional evidence that patients with HBeAg-negative CHB-LC

had a higher mortality rate than those of patients with HBeAg-positive by the PSM method. The particular strength of our study was the use of PSM to control the confounders in both groups. Thus, the conclusion was more convincing as compared with the previous studies. Moreover, the follow-up period in our study was about 3 years. However, there were several limitations of this study. First, the sample size was relatively small, so our conclusion needs to be confirmed in a larger sample. Second, the data of HBV genome mutations were not available in our study, so the effect of viral mutations on clinical outcomes needs to be validated. Third, we did not compare other clinical events, such as HCC development, between HBeAg-positive and HBeAg-negative patients. Fourth, the survival analysis in patients with compensated LC was not conducted because few deaths occurred in this group. Thus, the impact of HBeAg status on prognosis of patients with compensated LC needs to be confirmed in a future study. Fifth, we did not compare the incidence of decompensation events between HBeAg-positive and HBeAg-negative patients since these data were not available. Sixth, antiviral treatment could have affected the progression and outcomes of LC. In the present study, patients might have initiated or modified antiviral treatment during the follow-up, which might have biased our results. Seventh, since the level of serum creatine and the incidence rate of hepatic encephalopathy in HBeAg negative patients were higher than HBeAg positive patients, the results need to confirm in a large sample cohort study in future. Finally, the confounders including the length of course after diagnosing LC, the periods of anti-HBV treatment, drug resistance, initiating anti-HBV before or after diagnosing LC were not analyzed in this study. Thus, our results need to be validated in future study.

In summary, our results suggested that HBeAg-negative CHB-LC patients had a higher liver-related mortality than HBeAg-positive CHB-LC patients. However, the findings need to be validated in future studies.

Significant Statement

HBeAg has always been considered as an important biomarker of immune status in patients with chronic hepatitis B (CHB). However, the association of HBeAg status with the long-term progression of patients with CHB-related cirrhosis remains controversial. This study demonstrated that HBeAg negative status was significantly associated with increased risk of liver-related mortality in patients with CHB-related cirrhosis. Our results may provide evidence for the individualized management of CHB-related cirrhosis patients.

Abbreviations

ALB, albumin; ALT, alanine aminotransferase; AS, ascites; CHB, chronic hepatitis B; CI, confidence interval; CTP, Child–Turcotte–Pugh; EVB, esophageal variceal bleeding; HBeAg, hepatitis B e antigen; HBV, hepatitis B virus; HCC, hepatocellular carcinoma; HE, hepatic encephalopathy; HR, hazard ratio; IQR, interquartile range; LC, liver cirrhosis; MELD, model for end-stage liver disease; PSM, propensity score matching; PT, prothrombin time; Tbil, total bilirubin level.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no conflicts of interest exist.

Authors' contributions

All authors contributed to this study at different levels. All authors read and approved the final version. Study concept and design (CW, RH, CWZ, JW); acquisition of data (JW, SXY, LZ, JCL, RFX, YG, JX, YLX, WHW, XT, XMY, YXC); statistical analysis and interpretation of data (JW, RH); drafting of the manuscript (JW, RH); critical revision of the manuscript for important intellectual content (RH, CW).

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